

GEO-TOURISM DEVELOPMENT AS A MEANS OF REDUCING RURAL UNEMPLOYMENT IN ESAN WEST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF EDO STATE.

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Abstract

With the present unemployment rate in Nigeria, it is clear that “feeding bottle” federalism where it seems there is much to share and little to contribute can no longer be sustained. There is therefore an urgent need for alternate source of income other than oil. The need for diversification in Nigeria is now more compelling, judging by the number of graduates being rolled out from the various institutions, seeking for non-existence white collar jobs. Tourism therefore presents an alternative source of revenue in Esan West local government area. The aim of this paper is to examine tourism as a panacea against unemployment, and a way out of poverty in the country, particularly in the rural areas, in Esan West Local Government. The study revealed that rural areas like Ogwa and Ujogba in the locality, are blessed with both natural and cultural endowments which are capable of improving their living standards. In view of this, Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to analyze the correlation between tourism business and other occupations (Teaching and farming,) in the study area. In the analysis, tourism was taken as the independent variable while other occupations (teaching and farming) as the dependent variables. The results revealed that employment in tourism have

significant and positive effects on employment in teaching which is ($r=0.739$) and farming ($r=0.728$) which are socio-economic indicators. The study recommends that there should be immediate mobilization of people towards the development of their natural and cultural resources for the development of tourism, and the construction of infrastructural facilities.

Key words: geo-tourism, panacea, economic meltdown, rural area, poverty.

Introduction

Geo-tourism according to the National Geographical Society (NGS), said that "tourism sustains or enhances the geo-graphical character of a place - its environment, culture, aesthetics, heritage, and the *well-being* of its residents". It goes beyond "drive through travel" by focusing on the meaning of "place," as the community becomes a full partner in giving the visitor an authentic, enriching experience. The concept emphasizes local culture, products and traditions, and offers visitors multiple opportunities to explore an area's natural beauty and human community. The idea is that all elements of a place's geographical character work together to create an experience that is richer than the sum of its parts, appealing to visitors with diverse interests. Geo-tourism builds on a destination's "sense of place," to emphasize the distinctiveness of its locale and benefit visitors and residents alike (<https://www.crowndiscoverycenter.com/geo-tourism-information/>).

The United Nation World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) defines tourists as "people who travel to and stay in place outside their usual environment for not more than one consecutive year for leisure, business and other purposes not related to the exercise of an activity remunerated from within the place visited". The World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) predict that the twenty-first-century economy would be dominated by three industries: telecommunications, information technology, and tourism. The travel and tourism industry has

grown by 500% in the last 25 years (<https://tourismnotes.com/travel-tourism/>). Many rural areas in Nigeria contain valuable reservoir of skills and abilities as well as space and other physical resources which, if mobilized, offer potential for endogenous and self-reliant development in tourism, (Awartefe, 2005). Tourism has been reported to be a major resource and foreign exchange earner, indeed, the second single item after crude oil in the world trade, (Awartefe, 2005). Since this industry has been identified as a veritable alternative towards transforming the rural communities, Esan West Local Government could as well adopt this option to improve their living condition.

The state of tourism and rural development in Nigeria when viewed in the context of global trend has suffered setbacks in that tourism which ought to be a traditional source of job creation and income in Nigeria has suffered neglect, low community pricing, apathy and obscurity, (Awartefe, 2005).

Jiboku *et. al*, (2010) opined that substantial numbers of tourism centers in Nigeria are located in the rural areas and with the biting economic hardships, consequent upon the global economic melt-down, tourism more than ever before has become the most viable option for nations. Levis (1998) adds that the process of tourism development begins when an individual or organization believes that there is a resource in the area that would be of interest to the tourists and such a resource could be natural or man-made. Many rural areas particularly Esan West Local Government area contain valuable reservoir of tourism centers which, if mobilized, offer potential for endogenous and self-reliant development. Tourism has been reported to be a major resource of foreign exchange earner, indeed, the second single item after crude oil in the world trade, (Awartefe, 2005). Since this industry has been identified as a veritable alternative towards transforming the rural communities, Esan West Local

Government could as well adopt this option to improve their living condition.

Tourism resource takes different forms in Nigeria and it has been grouped into four sub-groupings by Adejuwon viz: a) Biogenic or vegetal tourism resources (Trees, Animals and Birds) b. Water Tourism Resources (Rivers, waterfalls, springs and streams) c. Landscape Tourism Resources (Scenic landscapes, pleasing unpolluted weather, hills, valleys, etc.) d. Festivals and cultural Tourism Resources (cultural festivals, social events, annual tribal rituals, traditional celebrations and cultural games) (Adejuwon, 1993).

In spite of the so many benefits of tourism, there are several problems to the development of tourism in the rural places of Nigeria (Awartefe, 2005). These problems are: political, social, economic, religious as well as cultural amongst others. As far back as 1976, Areola (1976) noted that “it may sound incredible that Nigeria has up to 33 game reserves most of which are not functional”. Awartefe (2005) gave a detailed evaluation of tourism resource areas in Nigeria and identified eight tourist regions with 99 tourist attractions most of which are in the rural areas of Nigeria. It is regrettable to note that despite the abundant natural and human resources available for tourist attraction in Esan West Local Government area, it was not included in the earlier findings either by Areola,(1976) or Awartefe, (2005).

The implications of this total neglect and abandonment is the high unemployment and poverty level that is being experienced in Esan West in particular and other rural communities of Nigeria in general. According to Odeleye and Oyekanmi (2013), the nauseating aspect of this case is that personalities in Nigeria like lawmakers, Governors, ministers and such other top politicians and captains of industries jets out of this country with their families at the slightest opportunity to enjoy the same thing (tourist attractions) in foreign countries which they refuse to develop in their country. This could be the reason why,

Oaikhena (2021) observed that “...the restriction of national planning efforts towards economic development, is scantily referenced to social, political and cultural development which often times is recorded in Africa”. For instance, the former President of Nigeria, Muhamandu Buhari in 2017 spent 103 days on medical trip abroad when such hospital could be built in the rural areas of Nigeria, to serve as tourism destination as well as provide world class health facilities. Apart from the medical treatment that such a place will provide, the serenity of the environment can both be a tourist center as well as provide healing balms to the sick; physically, psychologically, mentally and emotionally (Odeleye and Oyekanmi, 2013). It is against this backdrop that this study intends to show how tourism development can help reduce the present unemployment situation in Esan West, Edo State, Nigeria.

Study area and location

Study area

Esan west Local Government Area is one of the (18) Local Government Areas in Edo State. It was carved out of the defunct Okpebho Local Government Area of Bendel State in 1991 by the military government of Ibrahim B. Babangida. It has a land area of about 502km² a total population of 127,718 out of which 65,312 of them are male and 62,406 are female, (NPC Report,2006). The study area is Esan West Local Government Area which has 6 autonomous kingdoms. The prominent kingdoms in the Local Government Area are: Ekpoma, Ogwa, Ujogba, Urhoi, Egoro and Idoa traditionally ruled by monarchs including small and large villages such as Iruokpen, Ile, Ukpenu, Emuhi, Ujiemen, Uhiele, Emaudo, Upper Izogen, Ebute, Uke among other smaller localities (Aimienwanlen, 1990). Esan west people are hospitable, peace-loving, and believe strongly in self-help, thus assisting one another to achieve development. They are equally fun-loving people who have various festivities and

ritualistic traditions like the famous Igbabonelinmhin, Asologun, Oleke, Akpazi, traditional wrestling as well as rivers (Ibiekuma, Ihunmogbe, Azido, Eralua) palaces, colorful marriage developed. Their folktales and folklores serve as forms of learning and entertainment, costumes, commemorative statues among others which could be that these communities are politically grouped into 10 wards Fig (i.i) viz:

Location

Relief

The local relief of the area on the average is about 150metres above sea level. However, some areas are as low as 20metres above sea level. Esanland generally where Esan west belongs has been identified as the source or head water of many streams and rivers some of which flow into the Benin lowlands while others flow northwards into the river Niger, (Segynola, 2011).

Population

Esan west has a total population of 127,718 inhabitants with 65,312 male and 62,406 female, (NPC Census report, 2006). This figure is projected to 2024 using 2.8 percent. The formula is:

$$Pt_0 = pt_1 e^{rt}$$

Where: pt_0 = population of the base year (2006)

Pt_1 = population of the present (new) year (i.e 2024)

e = Exponential function (2.718)

t = time difference (i.e. 2024- 2006 = 18 years)

r = projected growth rate in percentage (i.e. 2.8 NPC 2006)

1 = constant

Applying this formula in Esan west with a base year (2006) population of 127,718 at growth rate of 2.8 percent, the projection yielded 209,956 people. The calculation is as follows:

$$\frac{2.8}{100} = 0.028$$

$$100$$

$$1 + 0.028 = 1.028$$

Number of years (i.e. years between 2024-2006 =18)

$$\therefore 1.028^{18} = 1.6439025.$$

$$= 1.6439025 \times 127,718$$

$$= 209,955.943.$$

Therefore, population projection for Esan west population projection by year 2024 is estimated at 209,956 people.

Conceptual framework and literature review

Conceptual framework

The conceptual framework used in this research is the anti-poverty framework for rural development by (Richie et al, 2006). This anti-poverty tourism framework identifies the poor who are in most cases the local communities in poor countries such as Nigeria. In order for tourism development to successfully contribute to poverty reduction, the framework suggests three interrelated factors that should be taken seriously.

Fig.3.1. An integrated anti-poverty framework for rural development.

Source Richie et al 2006

The first factor is to ensure that there is active local participation in the tourism development process. The second factor is to make the destination competitive so that it is able to attract a sufficient number of tourists. This reflects the argument that tourists are not drawn to the rural area simply to stay with local communities but because of the “attraction base” available which will provide the type of experiences that satisfy their desire (Garrod, 2006). The third factor is to ensure that the destination is sustainable to promise viable tourism business.

The framework of Ritchie *et al* (2006), underline the fact that lack of any one of the above three factors or deficiency of it may limit the positive impact of tourism from reaching the poor. Having all the above factors in place, the framework further identifies three determinants which together with the previous factors may lead to poverty alleviation. The first determinant is the need to create economic opportunity which local communities must have access and can take advantage of, to change their lives. The second determinant is empowerment of local communities. This means strengthening the communities’ ability to act for themselves and to add their voices in the local decision – making process. It also aims at enhancing their capacity to influence their interest and engage, pursue and benefit from any economic opportunities. In particular, empowerment involves getting rid of the barrier that works against the local communities and building their capacity to engage effectively in markets (Ritchie,2006).

However, since the poor have limited financial capacity to tackle various risks, such as ill-health, economic shocks and natural disasters, creating an opportunity and empowerment are not enough. This could be the reason Oaikhena (2021) posits that “...social protection expenditures have a prominent role in reducing and preventing poverty, containing inequality and addressing social exclusion”. In this case, the third component which is security is fundamental to make the two earlier determinants accomplished the desired objectives of poverty alleviation (Ritchie et al, 2006). In simple terms, a social security system is needed to enable and empower local communities to alleviate poverty through tourism while protecting them against risks.

In Uganda for instance, until 2001, a number of adults were infected by HIV/AIDS (World Bank, 2000/ 2001). This explains that any effort by local communities in Uganda to reduce poverty, especially income poverty could be slowed down by the prevalence of disease. Therefore, in such a country, any anti-poverty framework that must work should include a social security component with a programme that aims to stop the spread of the disease; thereby reducing peoples vulnerability to risks of ill-health. In Nigeria and indeed Esan West,, a number of social security facilities have been put in place to enhance health quality, peace and tourism development such as: The Roll Back Malaria, Kick polio out of Nigeria, Mass Transit System, Sustainable Infrastructural Facilities, free test and treatment of people with HIV/AIDS among others which can help the people in the tourism destinations get prepared for tourism development implications; hence this framework is relevant. According to Molntosh *et al*, (2001), traditional and cultural tourism covers all aspects of travel where tourists learn about each other’s way of life and thoughts. This will include sites, which can be classified into the following categories: Traditional living styles, prehistoric and contemporary festivals, commemorations and entertainment.

It also includes arts and crafts, architecture, historic ruins, dancing, festivals, dress, cuisine, language and religion (Weaver *et al*, 2000).

A large part of rural tourism is about contact with other people's traditions and cultures which involves learning about others' tradition and cultures and learning about their way of life. Tradition and cultural tourism, which is more associated with the traditional beliefs of rural communities, is constantly growing as more and more tourists seek to interact with other cultures and broaden their knowledge and personnel experience base. It has been discovered that culture is an asset that communities own which can be marketed in a way that creates employments and attract investments and income (Weaver *et al*, 2000, Molntosh *et al*, 2001).

Since cultural and traditional tourism has the potential to restore the past, and its history, revitalize arts and skills, foster creativity and allow communities to present themselves positively, it is therefore vital that rural communities be assisted and encouraged to actively maintain and nurture their own cultures and traditions lest they become obsolete. Tradition and cultural tourism actively markets that which makes a community unique. Many tourists are interested in the way things are in their natural states which is why traditional people with their cultural villages and traditional museums are popular. Tradition and cultural tourism coffers a number of benefits in those who are involved in it. For the host community, it brings development and those who experienced it satisfy their curiosity and achieves fulfillment while improving their knowledge. The tourists are looking for information about the history of a people, their traditional lifestyle, how such people are living now, their arts and crafts, dances, authentic or traditional cuisine (food) and in addition, actual direct contact with indigenous communities and participation in traditional activities. As it is, one of the aims of this study is to examine the Esan culture (festivals, dances, arts and culture), with

a view to finding out those that could be developed for tourism purposes.

Community empowerment types in tourism development

Schyvens (2000) suggested that “when outside controls turn to local controls, many benefits become apparent”. These benefits can include economic, psychological, social and political empowerments. Community empowerment according to Raid (2004), is the process of increasing personal, inter-personal and political power, enabling individuals to their situations. Empowerment increases the energy, motivation and problem-solving skills, decision making power, self-esteem, self-sufficiency, and self-determination of community members.

Telfer (2008) holds that empowerment means enabling poor communities to build their capacity and their confidence to succeed at community development level in an effective and sustainable manner. It is a means by which community develop consensus. It is open, transparently managed and perpetuated by the community. He adds that community empowerment means far more than having access to social plan by donors and government, rather; capacity building needs to be strengthened and built. According to Oaikhena and Ajagun (2015), they observed that “...members of a community must continually remind themselves that real development happens only when community members make decisions and take action to achieve their own vision for community transformation”. The objectives of community transformation and empowerment is to encourage community to be self-reliant, build individual skills and develop community solidarity as well as build confidence in the community’s ability to control its ultimate destiny.

Fig. 3.2: Potentials for host community in the tourism development process

Types	of	Signs	of	Signs	of	dis-
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empowerment	empowerment	empowerment
Economic	Tourism brings lasting economic gains to a local community. Cash earned is shared between many households in the community. There are visible signs of improvements from the cash that is earned.	Tourism merely results in small spasmodic cash gains for a local community. Only a few individuals or families gain direct financial benefits from tourism, while others cannot find a way to share in the economic benefits because they lack capital, experience or the appropriate skills.
Psychological	Self-esteem of many community members is enhanced because of the outside recognition of the uniqueness and value of their culture, their natural resources and their and their traditional knowledge. Access to employment and cash lead to an increase in status for traditionally low status rung of the society, e.g. the youth and the poor.	Those who interact with the tourists are left feeling that their culture and way of life are inferior. Many people do not share in the benefits of tourism, and are thus confused, frustrated, uninterested or disillusioned with the initiative.
Social	Tourism maintains or enhances the local community's	Disharmony and social decay. Many in the community take on

	<p>equilibrium. Community cohesion is improved as individuals and families work together to build a successful tourism venture. Some funds raised are used for community development purposes; e.g. to build school or increase and improve water supplies.</p>	<p>outside values and lose respect for traditional culture norms and values and for their elders. Disadvantaged groups such as women and children bear the brunt of the problems associated with the tourism initiative and fail to share equitably in its benefits. Rather than cooperating, families, ethnics or social-economic groups compete with each other for the perceived benefits of tourism. Resentment and jealousy are commonplace.</p>
<p>Political</p>	<p>The community's political structures fairly represent the needs and interest of all community groups. The opinions of a variety of community groups are sought and they are provided with opportunities to be represented on decision making bodies.</p>	<p>The community has an autocratic and /or self-interested leadership. The local community is not involved in decision making so the majority of community members feels they have little or no say over whether the tourism initiative operates or the way in which it operates.</p>

Source: Scheyvens, (2002).

Researchers recognized the importance of involving the host community in tourism and the benefits that can arise. However, there are varying opinions on how community participation should take form. This is reflected by Mitchell *et al* (2001), who states that “while scholars, entrepreneurs, and practitioners are beginning to understand the need for placing greater emphasis on community empowerment in tourism planning and implementation, little work has been done on the details of execution”. This demonstrates the need to conduct further research which examines the role of the host community in the tourism development process and subsequently the impacts this has on the community.

Literature review

Tourism as a means of reducing unemployment in the world over cannot be over emphasized, judging from our review of literatures such as the works of Andreck, K. L., and G. P. Nyaupane (2011), Baloch, Q. B., S. N. Shah, N. Iqbal, et al. (2023), Dat, L. T., H. C. Wu, T. Li, W. Huang, G. Liou, and C. Hsieh. (2024), Gannon (1994), Greffe (1994) and Sharpley & Sharpley (1997), which provides comprehensive lists of the benefits of rural tourism and geo-tourism. The growth of geo-tourism has an impact on the lives of locals in the area (Gautam, V., 2023). The above literatures suggest that rural geo-tourism acts as a source of employment, resulting in a primary source of income for individuals and acts as additional income for individuals (Sharpley and Sharpley, (1997); Riberio *et al* (2002); MacDonald *et al* (2003), Liu (2006).

Geo-tourism benefits locals by promoting local services and assets, while responding to visitors' needs by educating residents and showing them the true value of their own hometown like the Fogo Island, Newfoundland using the geo-tourism to build itself by adapting traditional material, food, and designs.

Geo-tourism like sustainable tourism protects its most valuable asset - the destination itself. It seeks to avoid the "loved to death" syndrome by anticipating development pressures and implementing limits and management techniques that preserve natural habitats and views, heritage sites, community traditions and its conserves resources (*Fuchs, Christopher; Schreier, Martin (2011)*).

Environmentally conscious travelers, patronize businesses that reduce pollution and waste, energy consumption, water usage, etc, and it also respects local customs and history. Foreign visitors learn local etiquette, including common phrases in the local language. Residents learn how to accommodate foreign expectations that may differ from their own. It aims for quality and benefits for all. Destinations measure tourism success not just by the number of visitors, but by their length of stay, how they spend their money, and the quality of their experience. Geo-tourism is synergistic: The complex elements of geographical character work together to create a tourist experience richer than the sum of its parts, appealing to visitors with diverse interests. It involves the community, local businesses as civic groups cooperate in the interest of a distinctive, authentic visitor experience and create unforgettable enthusiastic visitor's return with exciting new information and understanding and their stories encourage others to plan their own adventure which creates healthy business for the destination (Four Corners Region, Geo-tourism Stewardship Council). Available at Susanethomas@earththink.net.

Fuchs, et al (2011) on Customer opined that "customers who are empowered to select their products to be marketed by a firm expresses stronger demand for the underlying products compared to customers without such empowerment". The development of geo-tourism is said to serve as a lever for a whole chain of activities-as there becomes an increased need for goods and services to accommodate tourist needs- such as support for

existing and new businesses and services. In turn, this diversifies and strengthens the local economy and provides a more stable economic base for the local community (Gannon, 1994; Huang et al (1996) and Riberio et al (2002). The goal of developing tourism in rural areas is to attract tourist from outside the close vicinity of the destination. Attracting outsiders to a destination translates into bringing new money into the area which in turn stimulates the local economy, Greffe (1994).

This supports the notion “selling what we can produce to produce what we can sell”. This development has always attended to the economic needs of the rural localities including striving for authenticity, improving human value and ecological stability of the rural areas where tourism have been developed.

In addition to the economic benefits of rural tourism, the literature also suggests that the development of rural tourism can contribute to a number of social benefits to rural communities. These benefits include the provision of recreational opportunities, facilities, services and amenities that the rural community can benefit from which would otherwise be unavailable. Garrod et al (2006), assert that rural tourism has the ability to foster pride in the community, to provide an opportunity for cultural exchange and to create conditions for safeguarding and enhancing local cultural identities. Similarly, Sharpley and Sharpley (1997), suggested that rural communities can benefit from the development of tourism as it will enable the revitalization of local customs, crafts and cultural identities. And finally, it will repopulate the area which is often typified as having a declining and older community.

The countryside is often the main draw to attracting tourists to rural areas, thus, the physical environment is an important component to the success of rural tourism. It is agreed that developing tourism in rural areas can play a key role in revitalizing the natural, cultural and historical resources of the area (Gannon, 1994; Sharpley and Sharpley, 1997). Rural tourism

especially geo-tourism is said to have the ability to stimulate the conservation, protection and improvement of these important resources. These benefits collectively perpetuate the “promise of rural tourism” notion and explain why the “promotion of rural tourism is derivative of political will” Liu, (2006).

Methodology

The methods of data collection used in this research include: primary and secondary sources. The primary sources are questionnaire administration, personal oral interview, direct field observations, focus group discussion and the base map of the study area while the secondary sources include books, journals, National Population Commission, magazines and internet.

The statistical technique used in this research work is Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation analysis. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to compare the number of employments in tourism business in relation to each of the other types of occupation such as teaching and farming in the study area.

Spatial frame and sample size

The ten (10) wards in the study area formed our spatial frame while the sample size 1% of the number of households in Esan West. This is tabulated in table 4.1 below

S/no	Wards	Population	Households	Sample size
	Communities		No of households	1% of the households
1	OGWA	8,855	1,929	19
2	Ujogba/Ebute	8,344	1,820	18
3	Egoro/Idoa/Ukhun	10,609	2,471	25
4	Eguare/Emaudo	24,786	5,487	55
5	Ihinmidumu/ Ujemen	24,842	5,488	55
6	Iruekpen	20,934	3,363	34

7	Ukpenu/Emuhi	10,529	2,456	24
8	Urohi	7,695	1,684	17
9	Uhiele	5,263	1,167	12
10	Ileh	5,873	1,304	13
TOT AL		127,718	27,169	272

Source: National Population Commission, (NPC) Benin City, Edo State

Results and discussion

The Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to analyze the correlation between geo-tourism business and other occupations (teaching and farming) in the study area. In our analysis, tourism was taken as the independent variable while other occupations (teaching and farming) as the dependent variable.

Hypothesis

HO: That there is no significant relationship between Tourism business development and improvement in the socio-economic living condition in the rural areas.

HI: That there is.

Table 5.1. Correlation between employment in tourism and other occupations (teaching and farming) in the study area.

Dependent variables	Tourism	
	Correlation coefficient	Probability level
Teaching	.739*	.015
Farming	.728*	.027

**Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). (r = 0.632)*

Source: Author’s fieldwork.

The results from *Table 5.1* revealed that employment in tourism have significant relationship with employment in teaching which is ($r = 0.739$) and farming which is ($r = 0.728$). Since the computed correlation is greater than the tabulated at the 5% level ($r = 0.632$), we therefore accept the alterative hypothesis that: There is significant correlation between tourism business and other occupations (Teaching and farming) in the study area. This

implied that if tourism business is fully developed in Esan West, its multiplier effects will bring about development in other employments such as teaching and farming. In the case of teaching, this is possible because tourism attracts other social infrastructural and social amenities like (schools, recreation centres, road, water, police station, parks etc), schools will be attracted to the area and more teachers will be employed. Similarly, when tourism is well developed, and the above amenities are provided, more people who went to the cities from the village for white-collar jobs and have none after all, will have reasons(s) to return back and start farming and their crafts since they are now sure that tourists will buy their farm produce and this will increase the number of people in the farming business.

Summary and Conclusion

Our summary of findings in terms of basic socio-economic indicators, revealed that, most of the people in the study area live under poor conditions; lacking the basic things of life such as good shelter, food, clothing and good water owing to unemployment. There is certainly a compelling need to kick-start a business which can accommodate majority of the people without necessarily changing their location or environment which is geo-tourism.

The communities in the study area have for a long time been suffering from poverty and deprivations leading to poor living standards. They remained relatively stagnant in terms of employment, good housing and other social amenities, resulting in the deterioration of their social-economic living conditions. Consequently, they are willing and ready to change their present status for a better living condition. This study also revealed that most of the communities in the study area continue to live under poor socio-economic conditions. The ready answer to this lies in geo-tourism development since geo-tourism business has the

capacity to employ the skilled and the unskilled, male or female and the old or young in their present locations.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made for the improvement and development of the socio-economic well-being of the people in Esan West Local Government Area of Edo State with regards to tourism.

- i. Immediate mobilization of the 209,956 people towards the development of their natural and cultural resources for the development of geo-tourism and for the improvement of their socio-economic well-being.
- ii. Development and construction of infrastructural facilities like roads, electricity, pipe-borne water, recreational facilities, schools, police stations, hospital among others for the 209, 956 population of the people in Esan west.
- iii. The media and Esan West authority should synergize by advertising the local government as a geo-tourism viable destination by educating and enlightening the people on the tourism potentials of Esan West Local Government Area.
- iv. The encouragement of the people to form themselves into groups in line with their endowments in the various communities and be encouraged to visit such areas as Ikogosi warm spring in Ekiti State, Obudu Cattle Ranch in Cross River State etc, to help them gather experiences from existing tourist destinations.
- v. Government should show more interest in the development of communities identified to possess such natural and cultural resources which are capable of attracting tourists to the local government.

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